

Implementation of a Daily Telemetry Renewal Protocol

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Background

- Alarm Fatigue-clinicians exposed to high # of alarms become desensitized and fail to respond (Keller, 2012). Alarm fatigue leads to patient deaths.
- Providers' over-prescription - #1 factor contributing to alarm burden and alarm fatigue.
- The AHA published Telemetry Practice Guidelines in 2004, but provider awareness and adherence is low.

Purpose

The purpose of this project was to develop, implement and evaluate a daily telemetry renewal protocol based on AHA telemetry practice guidelines to decrease unnecessary telemetry use and alarm fatigue.

Supporting Framework

- Iowa Model of EBP was used as the model.
- Iowa Model serves to overcome barriers in changing current routine healthcare practice.

Methods

Setting:

- 36-bed neurosciences unit at a 300-bed acute care facility in Southern California; unit averages 28-36 patients per day.
- Central monitoring station with 1 monitor watcher per 12-hour shift.
- All patients with telemetry orders remain on telemetry until discontinued by a provider.

Participants:

- Providers (physicians and nurse practitioners) from a hospitalist group.

Project Process

Step One: Retrospective Data Analysis

- Analyzed hospital patient & telemetry census from 9/1/17 to 1/1/18 to identify unit with highest telemetry utilization.

Step Two: Development of Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet

- Developed order sheet based on AHA's criteria.
- Customized parameters to fit characteristics of patients on the neurosciences unit.

Step Three: Retrospective Data Presentation

- Project proposal and retrospective data presented to stakeholders.
- Obtained informed consent from participating providers.

Step Four: Implementation

- Implemented protocol on all hospitalist patients on the neurosciences unit for 15 days.
- Each day, order sheet placed in the chart for providers to complete.

Step Five: Safety Monitoring

- Actionable cardiac events after each telemetry discontinuation was monitored.

Physician Daily Telemetry Renewal Order Sheet

The American Heart Association's Telemetry Practice Guidelines recommend Continuous Telemetry Monitoring according to criteria based on a Class System as follows. (The guidelines have been modified to fit the population on 3N)

Telemetry Renewal Recommended:	
CLASS I	2nd and 3rd degree AV block Acute Coronary Syndrome with high grade lesion awaiting intervention Acute heart failure/pulmonary edema Long QT syndrome Wolff-Parkinson-White syndrome with rapid anterograde conduction Severe hypokalemia or hypomagnesemia Administration of antiarrhythmic drugs known to cause torsade de pointes Acute stroke (48 hours)
CLASS II	Chest pain syndromes Presence of arrhythmia with active arrhythmia medication titration Syncope At risk for cardiac arrest, respiratory arrest, or development of hypotension

Telemetry Discontinuation recommended:

CLASS III	Absence of arrhythmia for 48 hours 48 hours after acute neurological event (syncope, stroke) without arrhythmias Clinical stabilization of acute decompensated heart failure Resolution of arrhythmias by medical therapy or device Negative cardiac enzymes and stress test in chest pain patients No further chest pain in uncomplicated MI patients (under observation for 2-4 days post MI)
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Physician Orders:

	Discontinue telemetry (no telemetry needs identified)
	Continue telemetry Rationale: (list diagnosis):

Telemetry Renewal Recommended:

Name: _____ Signature: _____

Patient Label _____ Date: _____

Key Results

- Average age of patients = 64 years (SD = 19.03), range from 28 - 99 years.
- 65 females (41.93%) and 89 males (57.7%).
- Average length of stay = 5.1 days (SD = 4.88).
- 11 patients (5.8%) uninsured (all of them under 65).
- Average decrease in telemetry use was 17.9% (SD = 14.85).

Discussion

- Cardiac monitoring needs to be assessed daily by provider.
- Protocol resulted in fewer monitored patients and identified physician rationales in continuing monitoring.
- Age was #1 rationale. Evidence lacking to guide telemetry use in patients over 75. Future research is needed to resolve this issue.
- All "agitated" patients received telemetry renewal orders as their activities needed to be monitored.
- Other methods of monitoring may be more appropriate for some patients.

Implication for Practice

- Findings from this project demonstrated that a protocol for providers to revisit daily monitoring decreases over monitoring.
- Protocol can be built into the EMR system to automate a provider-based daily telemetry renewal practice.

Results

Patients on Telemetry not Meeting Protocol Criteria Before and After Protocol Implementation

